

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
ENTRANCE SEAT ALLOTMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT
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SYNOPSIS

This project Entrance Seat Allotment System is windows application in which students can register with their rank number for the entrance examination and the administrator can allot the seats for the students. Administrator can add the college details and he batch details. Using this software the entrance seat allotment became easier and can be implemented using system. The main advantage of the project is the computerization of the entrance seat allotment process. Administrator has the power for the allotment. He can add the allotted seats into a file and the details are saved into the system. The total time for the entrance allotment became lesser and the allotment process became faster.

There are 11 modules in this project. They are:-

- Administrator Login
- Add College details
- View College details
- Delete College details
- Add Course
- View Course details
- Delete Course details
- Seat allotment Module
- Show allotment details
- Input Candidate details
- Request for allotment

OBJECT ORIENTED SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT

INTRODUCTION

Object oriented Programming emphasized on the data rather than the algorithm. In the OOP, data is compartmentalized or encapsulated with the associated functions and this compartment or capsule called an object. In the OO approach, the problem is divided into functions.

OO language allows localization of data and code and restricts other objects from referring to its local region. OOP is centered around the concepts of objects, encapsulations, abstract data types, inheritance, polymorphism, message based communication, etc. An OO language views the data and its associated set of functions as an object and treats this combination as a single entity. Thus an object is visualized as a combination of data and functions, which manipulate them.

During the execution of a program, the objects interact with each other by sending messages and receiving responses. An object communication with other objects need not be aware of the internal working of the objects with which it interacts. An object can be manipulated through an interface that responds to a few messages. The object's internal structure is totally hidden from the user and this property is called data/information hiding or data encapsulation.

The external interfaces are implemented by providing a set of methods, each of which accepts and responds to a particular kind of message. The methods defined in an object's class are the same for all objects belonging to that class but, the data is unique for each object.

Many object oriented analysis and object oriented design methodologies have emerged recently although the concepts underlying object orientation as a programming discipline has been developed long time ago. Object oriented methodologies represent a radical change over conventional methodologies such as structured analysis.

Various object-oriented methodologies can be best investigated by dividing them into two camps revolutionaries and synthesizes. Revolutionaries believe that object orientation is a radical change that renders conventional methodologies and ways of thinking obsolete. Synthesizes view object orientation as simply an accumulation of sound software engineering principles, which adopters can graft onto their existing methodologies with relative ease.

The revolutionaries state the following:

- There should be no doubt that OOD is fundamentally different from traditional structured design approaches, it requires a different way of thinking about decomposition, and it produces software architectures that are largely outside the realm of the structured design culture.
- There is no doubt one could arrive at the same results using different methods; same time but it is revealed that from experience that the thinking process, the discovery process, and the communication between the user and analyst are fundamentally different with OOA than with structured analysis.

On the other side the synthesis's states the following:

- Object oriented structured design methodology is essentially an elaboration of structured design. They state that the foundation of OOSD is structured design, and that structured design includes most if the necessary concepts and notations for OOSD.
- There is no doubt that object orientation has been touted as a revolutionary approach is a complete break with the past. OOA is a refinement of some the best software engineering ideas of the past.

The design of an object appears over a sequence of stages. It's helpful to have this perspective because you stop expecting perfection right away; instead you realize that the understanding of what an object does and what it should look like happens over time. This view also applies to the design of various types of programs; the pattern for a particular type of program emerges through struggling again and again with that problem. Objects too have their patterns that emerge through understanding, use and reuse.

1. **OBJECT DISCOVERY:** This stage occurs during the initial analysis of a program. Looking for external factors and boundaries, duplication of elements in the system, and the smallest conceptual units may discover objects. Some objects are obvious if you already have a set of class libraries. Commonality between classes suggesting base classes and inheritance may appear right away, or later in the design process.

2. **OBJECT ASSEMBLY:** As we are building an object we will discover the need for new members that didn't appear during discovery. The internal needs of the object may require other classes to support it.

3. **SYSTEM CONSTRUCTION:** Once again, more requirements for an object may appear at this later stage. As you learn you evolve our objects. The need for communication and interconnection with other objects in the system may change the needs of our classes or require new classes. For example we may discover the need for facilitator or helper classes, such as a linked list, that contain little or no state information and simply help other classes function.

4. **SYSTEM EXTENSION:** As we add new features to a system we may discover that your previous design doesn't support easy system extension. With this new information, you can restructure parts of the system, possibly adding new classes or class hierarchies.

5. **OBJECT REUSE:** This is the real stress test for a class. If someone tries to reuse it in an entirely new situation, they will probably discover some shortcomings. As you change a class to adapt to more new programs, the general principles of the class will become clearer, until you have a truly reusable type. However don't expect most object from a system design to be reusable-it is perfectly acceptable for the bulk of your object to be system-specific. Reusable types tend to be less common, and they must solve more general problems in order to be reusable.

ADVANTAGES OF OBJECT ORIENTED PROGRAMMING.

- **Simplicity:** software objects model real world objects, so the complexity is reduced and the program structure is very clear.
- **Modularity:** each object forms a separate entity whose internal workings are decoupled from other parts of the system.
- **Modifiability:** it is easy to make minor changes in the data representation or the procedures in an OO program. Changes inside a class do not affect any other part of a program, since the only public interface that the external world has to a class is through the use of methods.
- **Extensibility:** adding new features or responding to changing operating environments can be solved by introducing a few new objects and modifying some existing ones.
- **Maintainability:** objects can be maintained separately, making locating and fixing problems easier.
- **Re-usability:** objects can be reused in different programs.

FEATURES OF OBJECT – ORIENTED PROGRAMMING

It is necessary to understand some of the concepts used extensively in object - oriented programming. These include:

- Objects
- Classes
- Data Abstraction and encapsulation
- Inheritance
- Polymorphism
- Dynamic binding
- Message Passing

We shall discuss these concepts in some detail in this Section.

Objects

Objects are the basic run – time entities in an object – oriented system. They may represent a person, a place, a bank account, a table of data or any item that the program has to handle. They may also represent user – defined data such as vectors, time and lists. Programming problem is analyzed in terms of objects and the nature of communication between them. Program objects should be chosen such that they match closely with the real – world objects.

Objects take up space in the memory and have an associated address like a record in Pascal, or a structure in C.

When a program is executed, the objects interact by sending message to one another. For example, if “customer” and “account” are two objects in a program, then the customer object may send a message to the account object requesting for the bank balance. Each object contains data, and code to manipulate the data. Objects can interact without having to know details of each other’s data or code. It is sufficient to know the type of message accepted, and the type of response returned by the objects. Although different authors represent them differently, shows tow notations that are popularly used in object – oriented analysis and design.

Classes

We just mentioned that objects contain data, and code to manipulate that data. The entire set of data and code of an object can be made a user – defined data type with the help of a class. In fact, objects are variables of the type class. Once a class has been defined, we can create any number of objects belonging to that class. Each object is associated with the data of type class with which they are created. A class is thus a collection of objects of similar type. For example, mango, apple and orange are members of the class fruit. Classes are user – defined data types and behave like the built – in types of a programming language. The syntax used to create an object is no different than the syntax used to cerate an integer object in C. If fruit has been defined as a class, then the statement.

Fruit mango;

Will create an object **mango** belonging to the class **fruit**

Data Abstraction and Encapsulation

The wrapping up of data and functions into a single unit (called class) is known as encapsulation. Data encapsulation is the most striking feature of a class. The data is not accessible to the outside world, and only those functions, which are wrapped in the class, can access it. These functions provide the interface between the object's data and the program. This insulation of the data from direct access by the program is called data hiding or information hiding.

Abstraction refers to the act of representing essential features without including the background details or explanations. Classes use the concept of abstraction and are defined as a list of abstract attributes such as size, weight and cost, and functions to operate on these attributes. They encapsulate all the essential properties of the objects that are to be created. The attributes are sometimes called data members because they hold information. The functions that operate on these data are sometimes called methods or member functions.

Since the classes use the concept of data abstraction, they are known as Abstract Data Types (ADT).

Inheritance

Inheritance is the process by which objects of one class acquire the prosperities of objects of another class. It supports the concept of hierarchical classification. For example, the bird 'robin' is a part of the class 'flying bird', which is again a part of the class 'bird'. The principle behind this sort of division is that each derived class shares common characteristics with the class from which it is derived as illustrated.

In OOP, the concept of inheritance provides the idea of reusability. This means that we can add additional features to an existing class without modifying it. This is possible by deriving a new class from the existing one. The new class will have the combined features of both the classes. The real appeal and power of the inheritance mechanism is that it allows the programmer to reuse a class that is almost, but not exactly, what he wants, and to tailor the class in such a way that it does not introduce any undesirable side – effects into the rest of the classes.

Note that each sub – class defines only those features that are unique to it. Without the use of classification, each class would have to explicitly include all of its features.

Polymorphism and Overloading

Polymorphism is another important OOP concept. Polymorphism, a Greek term, means the ability to take more than one form. An operation may exhibit different behavior in different instances. The behavior depends upon the types of data used in the operation. For example, consider the operation of addition. For two numbers, the operation will generate a sum. If the operands are strings, then the operation would produce a third string by concatenation. The process of making an operator to exhibit different behaviors in different instances is known as operator overloading.

Illustrates that a single function name can be used to handle different number and different types of arguments. This is something similar to a particular word having several different meanings depending on the context. Using a single function name to perform different types of tasks is known as function overloading.

Polymorphism plays an important role in allowing objects having different internal structures to share the same external interface. This means that a general class of operations may be accessed in the same manner even though specific actions associated with each operation may differ. Polymorphism is extensively used in implementing inheritance.

Dynamic Binding

Binding refers to the linking of a procedure call to the code to be executed in response to the call. Dynamic binding (also known as late binding) means that the code associated with a given procedure call is not known until the time of the call at run – time. It is associated with a polymorphic reference depends on the dynamic type of the reference.

Inheritance every object will have this procedure. Its algorithm is, however, unique to each object and so the draw procedure will be redefined in each class that defines the object. At run – time, the code matching the object under current reference will be called.

Message Passing

An object – oriented program consists of a set of objects that communicate with each other. The process of programming in an object – oriented language, therefore, involves the following basic steps.

1. Creating classes that define objects and their behavior.
2. Creating objects from class definitions, and
3. Establishing communication among objects.

Objects communicate with one another by sending and receiving information much the same way as people pass messages to one another. The concept of message passing makes it easier to talk about building systems that directly model or simulate their real – world counterparts.

A message for an object is a request for execution of a procedure, and therefore will invoke a function (procedure) in the receiving object that generates the desired result. Message Passing involves specifying the name of the object, the name of the function (message) and the information to be sent.

Objects have a life cycle. They can be created and destroyed. Communication with an object is feasible as long as it is alive.

IDENTIFICATION OF NEEDS

Object-oriented programming promises to solve many key problems of software engineering like reuse, extensibility, and maintainability. Adding to the initial costs of software purchase are often considerable software maintenance costs. Object-Oriented Software Construction gives a breakdown of these costs, based on a survey of 487 installations developing various application software.

The high percentage of changing user requirements is not surprising in view of the rapid technology changes and increasing user expectations. The high costs involved reflect on conventional software and its inability to cope with change. Software quality aspects can be grouped into internal and external quality factors. The internal quality factors apply to the "inner workings" of software modules such as modularity or readability, and are generally of not much concern to the end user of the software, unless the user is concerned with self-developed extensions.

Of more importance for the end user are external factors such as:

Correctness: - The ability of software products to exactly perform their tasks, as defined by the requirements and specifications.

Robustness: - The ability of software systems to function even in abnormal conditions.

Extendibility: - The ease with which software products may be adapted to changes of specifications.

Reusability: - The ability of software products to be reused, in whole or in part, for new applications.

Compatibility: - The ease with which software products may be combined with others.

OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE

OBJECTIVES

Common Allotment System (CAS) is an application software developed for speeding up the process of allotment for engineering and medical entrance through computerization. It is developed in an Object Oriented Language, C++. The system consists of two modules – administrator (entrance exam controller) and user (candidate). A user can enter their rank and their preference for getting a suitable college and branch. An administrator can check the details of each candidate and allot them as per their requirements and qualifications. So the system gives maximum feasible solution for the common seat allotment process

SCOPE

Now a day the entrance allotment is done manually and it takes more than a month to allot seat correctly to every students. But the allotment is done manually and it makes some errors in the allotment process. The main advantage of the project is the error free software for the allotment process. The entrance allotment make system based and the error free output with in a limited amount of time. The allotment details are stored in the files and every student can view the seat details in each college. The details of the college are entered by the administrator and the details of the allotment are viewed by the colleges and students.

Hardware and Software Specifications

PROCESSOR

CPU	:	PENTIUM IV
SPEED	:	2 GHz
COPROCESSOR	:	BUILT IN

MEMORY

TOTAL RAM	:	128 MB
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STORAGE

DISKETTE A	:	1.44MB FLOPPY 3.5"
HARD DISK	:	40 GB

INPUT DEVICES

KEYBOARD	:	105 KEYS
MOUSE	:	LOGITECH MOUSE

OUTPUT DEVICES

DISPLAY	:	SGVA COLOR
PRINTER	:	HP DESK JET
FRONT END	:	C++
OPERATING SYSTEM	:	WINDOWS XP

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

OOP FEATURES IMPLEMENTED

The OOP features included in our project their definitions and how they are implemented are described below.

CLASS

Class is a way of binding the data and functions of an entity. It makes a data type used to create objects of this type. Objects are variables of type class. Once a class has been defined we can create any number of objects belonging to that class.

DATA HIDING, ENCAPSULATION & ABSTRACTION

Data members in our class are declared as private, which means that the data members are not accessible outside the class. Public member functions are used for accessing those private data members thereby implementing data hiding and encapsulation in C++.

Wrapping up of data and functions into a single unit called class is known as encapsulation. The data is not accessible to outside world. The insulation of the data from direct access by the program is called data hiding.

Abstraction refers to the act of representing essential features without including background details. Classes use the concept of abstraction and are defined as a list of attributes and functions to operate on these attributes.

DYNAMIC BINDING

Dynamic binding means that the code associated with a given procedure call is not known until the time of the call at runtime in our software since there is no such requirement, this feature of OOP is not currently implemented.

POLYMORPHISM

Polymorphism is the ability to react differently when presented with different information, known as parameters. In a functional programming language the only way to complete two different tasks is to have two functions with different names. In our project Operator overloading is implemented.

CONSTRUCTOR

Constructor is a special member function which initializes the objects of its class. It will have the same name as its class. It is called constructor because it constructs the values of data members of the class. In our project the values of data members are initialized through constructor.

Module Description

Administrator Login

The only input is password. It is to login to the college (which includes add college details, view college details and delete it), course (which includes add course details, view course details and delete it) and allotment details.

Add College details

The inputs are college type, college code, college name and place.

View College Details

There is no input. It is to display the details such as name, type, code and place of college.

Delete College details.

The only input is college code. It deletes the details of the particular college.

Add Course

College code, course code, course name and total seat available.

View Course details

There is no input. It is to display details such as seat availability for merit and each reservation type.

Delete Course details

College code and course code. Delete the specified course from the record.

Seat allotment Module

It is to allot seats to the students with given ranks.

Show allotment details

To display the allotment after seat are allotted.

Input Candidate details.

It is to input candidate name, rank, and type of college, course preferred, and reservation if there is.

Request for allotment

It reads the rank no and code of 3 colleges according to preference.

DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

Level 0 DFD

DFD Administrator

DFD Student

SOURCE CODE

CARDMENU.H

```
#include<stdio.h>
#include<string.h>
#include<dos.h>
#include<process.h>
#include<ctype.h>
#include<fstream.h>
#include "CAS\intrfc.h"
#define ENTER    13
#define ESC      27
#define SPACE    32
#define UP_ARROW 72
#define DOWN_ARR 80

class CMenu
{
    char *menuItem;
    int length;
    CMenu **subMenu;
public:
    CMenu(char* = "");
    void addMenu(CMenu&);
    CMenu *showSubMenu(int ,int);
    void showMainMenu(int,int);
```

```

    const char *caption();

    int items();

    ~CMenu()
    {
        delete[] menuItem;
    }

};

const char *CMenu::caption(void){
    return menuItem;
}

int CMenu::items(void){
    return length;
}

CMenu::CMenu(char *item):menuItem(new char[strlen(item)+1])
{
    strcpy(menuItem,item);
    subMenu=NULL;
    length=0;
}

void CMenu:: addMenu(CMenu &mnu)
{
    length++;
    CMenu**temp= new CMenu*[length];

    for(int i=0;i<length-1;i++)

```

```

    {
        temp[i]= subMenu[i];
    }
temp[length-1]=&mnu;
delete []subMenu;
subMenu=temp;
}
CMenu *CMenu::showSubMenu(int x,int y)
{
    int maxWidth=5;
    int len;
    int sel=0;
    char ch;
    CMenu *selected=NULL;
    // To find the length of the longest menu item
    for(int i=0;i<length;i++)
    {
        len=strlen(subMenu[i]->menuItem);
        if(len>maxWidth)
        {
            maxWidth=len;
        }
    }

    int mainMenuFlag=0;

    // Flag used to identify the main menu for diff. color settings.
    if (x+maxWidth < 50)  mainMenuFlag=1;

```

```

Cwindow w(x-1,y-1,maxWidth+7,length+2);
if (mainMenuFlag==1)
{
    w.setAttributes(BLUE,WHITE,1,1);
}
else
{
    //      w.setAttributes(BROWN,BLUE,1,1);
}
w.showWindow();
while(1)
{
    for(i=0;i<length;i++)
    {
        if(i==sel)
        {

            if (mainMenuFlag==1)
            {
                gotoxy(33,5);
                textcolor(BROWN);
                textbackground(BLACK);
                cprintf("<< MAIN MENU >> ");
            }
            textbackground(RED);

```

```
        textcolor(YELLOW);
    }
    else
    {
        textbackground(WHITE);
        textcolor(RED);
    }
}
else
{
    if (mainMenuFlag==1)
    {
        textbackground(BLUE);
        textcolor(WHITE);
    }
    else
    {
        textbackground(RED);
        textcolor(BLACK);
    }
}
gotoxy(x+2,y+i);
if(subMenu[i]!=NULL)
{
    printf("%s ",subMenu[i]->menuItem);
```

```

        }
    }
    while(!kbhit() delay(100);
    flushall();
    ch=getch();
    if (ch==ESC)
    {
        Cwindow w1(x-1,y-1,maxWidth+9,length+3);
        w1.setAttributes(WHITE,WHITE,0,0);
        w1.showWindow();
        break;
    }
    if(ch==ENTER)
    {
        { // To print the title for each submenu
            char *s;
            gotoxy(33,5);
            textcolor(MAGENTA);
            textbackground(BLACK);
            int l=strlen(subMenu[sel]->menuItem);
            s=new char[l];
            for (int i=0;i<=l;i++)
            {
                if ((subMenu[sel]->menuItem[i]!='_')
                {
                    s[i]=toupper(subMenu[sel]->menuItem[i]);
                }
            }
        }
    }

```

```

                else
                {
                    s[i]=' ';
                }
            }
            cprintf(" %s ",s);
        }
        if (subMenu[sel]->items()){
            selected=subMenu[sel]-
>showSubMenu(x+maxWidth+10,y+length-2);
            if (!selected) continue;
        }
        else {
            selected=subMenu[sel];
        }
        break;
    }
    if(ch==0) ch=getch();
    if(ch==UP_ARROW)
    {
        sel--;
        if(sel<0) sel=length-1;
    }
    if(ch==DOWN_ARR)
    {
        sel++;
    }
}

```

```
        if(sel>length-1) sel=0;
    }

}

return selected;

}
```

FRTSCR.cpp

```
#define DOWN    '\x50'
#define UP      '\x48'
#define pixTOrc(x) (8*(x-1)) //convert pixel into row and col format

#include <stdlib.h>
#include <dos.h>
#include <conio.h>
#include <string.h>
#include <graphics.h>
#include <ctype.h>
#include <iostream.h>
#include <fstream.h>

void displayMe(int x,int y,const char *ch,int delayTime);
int get_password();
```

```

void end();
void loading();

void loading()
{
    //progressbar logic
    int i=1,j,cnt,clrflag=0;
    setcolor(LIGHTGRAY);
    j=160;
    cnt=5;

    for(i=j;i<420;i++)
    {
        gotoxy(35,25);
        //      cout<<cnt;
        rectangle(j,375,i,405);
        outtextxy(240,340,"LOADING ");
        if(i==(j+10))
        {
            j=j+13;
            i=j;

            if clrflag==1)
            {
                clrflag=0;
                setcolor(LIGHTGRAY);
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

        else
        {
            clrflag=1;
            setcolor(LIGHTBLUE);
        }
        cnt=cnt+5;
    }
}
delay(1000);
}

```

```

void displayMe(int x,int y,const char *ch,int delayTime)

```

```

{
    char d[2];
    int len=strlen(ch);

    for(int i=0;i<=len;i++)
    {
        d[0]=ch[i];
        d[1]='\0';
        outtextxy(x+pixTOrc((i+1)*2),y,d);
        delay(delayTime);
    }
}

```

```

int get_password()

```

```

{

```

```

setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,WHITE);
bar(0,0,640,480);

settextstyle(TRIPLEX_FONT,HORIZ_DIR,4);
setcolor(BLACK);
outtextxy(pixTOrc(15),pixTOrc(2),"ENTRANCE SEAT ALLOTMENT");

setfillstyle(LINE_FILL,6);
bar(pixTOrc(8),pixTOrc(7),pixTOrc(70),pixTOrc(7.5));
setcolor(GREEN);
settextstyle(3,HORIZ_DIR,3);
outtextxy(pixTOrc(20),pixTOrc(6),"Administrator Section");

int i,j;
setfillstyle(LINE_FILL,6);
for(i=5,j=80;i<40 || j>40;i++,j--)
{
    bar(pixTOrc(2),pixTOrc(10),pixTOrc(i),pixTOrc(55));
    delay(10);
    bar(pixTOrc(j),pixTOrc(10),pixTOrc(80),pixTOrc(55));
    //sound(400+(i*50));
    delay(10);
    //nosound();
}
setcolor(WHITE);
int c=pixTOrc(40),a=-1;
char pass[20],correctpassword[20]="admin";

```

```

setcolor(WHITE);
setttextstyle(TRIPLEX_FONT,HORIZ_DIR,3);
outtextxy(pixTOrc(16),pixTOrc(19),"Enter password : ");
setcolor(WHITE);

while (pass[a]!='\r')
{
    pass[++a]=getch();

    if (pass[a]=='\r' || a>=19)
    {
        pass[a]='\0';
        pass[++a]='\r';
        break;
    }

    c+=16;
    outtextxy(c,pixTOrc(20), "*");
}
if(strcmp(pass,correctpassword)==0)
{
    outtextxy(pixTOrc(20),pixTOrc(24),"Password Accepted");
    loading();
    return(0);
}
else
{

```

```

        outtextxy(pixTOrc(20),pixTOrc(24),"Wrong Password!!!");
        setcolor(WHITE);
        getch();
        return (1);
    }
}

void end()
{
    int i,j;
    setfillstyle(4,LIGHTRED);

    for(i=5,j=80;i<40 || j>40;i++,j--)
    {
        bar(pixTOrc(2),pixTOrc(10),pixTOrc(i),pixTOrc(55));
        delay(10);
        bar(pixTOrc(j),pixTOrc(10),pixTOrc(80),pixTOrc(55));
        //sound(400+(i*50));
        delay(10);
        //    nosound();
    }

    settextstyle(1,HORIZ_DIR,3);
    displayMe(pixTOrc(5),pixTOrc(18),"YOU ARE EXITING THE PROGRAM...",50);
    delay(500);
    settextstyle(1,HORIZ_DIR,3.5);
    displayMe(pixTOrc(8),pixTOrc(30),"THANK YOU!!!.....",50);
}

```

```
        setcolor(WHITE);
        delay(2000);
    }
```

INTRFC.cpp

```
#include<iostream.h>
#include<conio.h>
#include<stdio.h>
#include<string.h>
#include<dos.h>
#include<process.h>
#include<ctype.h>

#define ENTER    13
#define ESC      27
#define SPACE    32
#define UP_ARROW 72
#define DOWN_ARROW 80

void displayAt(int x, int y, int z)
{
    gotoxy(x,y);
    cout<<z<<endl;
}
```

```
void displayAt(int x, int y, float z)
```

```
{  
    gotoxy(x,y);  
    cout<<z<<endl;  
}
```

```
void displayAt(int x, int y, const char* z)
```

```
{  
    gotoxy(x,y);  
    cout<<z<<endl;  
}
```

```
class Cwindow
```

```
{  
    int left,top,width,height,backColor,textColor,borderStyle;  
    int shadowFlag;  
    char title[];  
    public:  
        Cwindow (int=0,int=0,int=0,int=0);  
        void setAttributes(int,int=3,int=0,int =0);  
        void showWindow ();  
        void setTitle(const char* =NULL,int=3);  
};
```

```
Cwindow::Cwindow (int l,int t, int w,int h):left(l),top(t),width(w),height(h)
```

```
{  
    backColor=YELLOW;
```

```

        textColor=WHITE;
        borderStyle=2;
    }

void Cwindow::setAttributes(int back, int text, int shadow,int border)
{
    backColor=back;
    textColor=text;
    shadowFlag=shadow;
    borderStyle=border;
}

void Cwindow::showWindow()
{
    char symbol[6];
    _setcursortype(_NOCURSOR);
    window(left,top,left+width,top+height);
    textbackground(backColor);
    textcolor (textColor);
    clrscr();
    window(1,1,79,24);
    if (borderStyle)
    {
        if (borderStyle==1)
        {
            symbol[0]='Ä';
            symbol[1]='³';
            symbol[2]='Ú';

```

```

        symbol[3]='ç';
        symbol[4]='À';
        symbol[5]='Û';
    }
    if (borderStyle==2)
    {
        symbol[0]='Í';
        symbol[1]='°';
        symbol[2]='Ê';
        symbol[3]='»';

        symbol[4]='Ë';
        symbol[5]='¼';
    }
    for(int i=left+1;i<left+width;i++)
    {
        gotoxy(i,top);
        //delay(10);
        printf("%c",symbol[0]);
    }

    gotoxy(left+width-1,top);
    printf("%c",symbol[3]);
    for( int j=top+1;j<top+height;j++)
    {
        gotoxy(left+width-1,j);
        //delay(10);
        printf("%c",symbol[1]);
    }
}

```

```

    }
    gotoxy(left+width-1,top+height);
    printf("%c",symbol[5]);
    for( j=left+width-2;j>left+1;j--)
    {
        gotoxy(j,top+height);
        //delay(10);
        printf("%c",symbol[0]);
    }
    gotoxy(left+1,top+height);
    printf("%c",symbol[4]);
    for(int k=top+height-1;k>top;k--)
    {
        gotoxy(left+1,k);
        //delay(10);
        printf("%c",symbol[1]);
    }
    gotoxy(left+1,top);
    printf("%c",symbol[2]);

}
}

void Cwindow::setTitle(const char* title,int color)
{
    int l=strlen(title);
    gotoxy((left+(width/2)-(l/2)),top+1);
    textbackground(backColor);

```

```

    textcolor(color);
    for(int i=0;i<1;i++)
    {
        cprintf("%c",title[i]);
        //delay(20);
    }
    char symbol;
    if(borderStyle==1) symbol='Ä';
    if(borderStyle==2) symbol='Í';
    textcolor(textColor);
    for ( i=left+3;i<(left+width-2);i++)
    {
        gotoxy(i,top+2);
        cprintf("%c",symbol);
    }
}

```

MAINCARD.cpp

```

#include <stdio.h>
#include <stdlib.h>
#include <dos.h>
#include <conio.h>
#include <string.h>
#include <graphics.h>
#include <ctype.h>
#include <iostream.h>

```

```
#include <fstream.h>
#include "CAS\cardmenu.h"
#include "CAS\frtscr.cpp"
#include "CAS\promenu.h"

void menu();

void menu1();

void firstmenu();

void graph();

void main()
{
    float y;
    clrscr();
    graph();
    firstmenu();
}

void menu()
{
    clrscr();
    closegraph();
    textbackground(WHITE);
    textcolor(BLUE);
    Cwindow w(1,1,79,23);
    gotoxy(3,25);
    printf("ESC -> previous menu");

    gotoxy(45,25);
```

```

cprintf(" UP / DOWN arrows + ENTER -> select");
w.showWindow();
w.setTitle(" ENTRANCE SEAT ALLOTMENT SYSTEM ",BLACK);

while(1)
{

    //window to display the menu
    Cwindow w1(5,4,71,18);
    w1.setAttributes(DARKGRAY,RED,0,1);
    w1.showWindow();
    w1.setTitle("",BLACK);
    CMenu main;
    CMenu main1("College ");
    CMenu main2("Course ");
    CMenu main3("Seat Allotment ");
    CMenu main4("Exit ");

    main.addMenu(main1);
    main.addMenu(main2);
    main.addMenu(main3);
    main.addMenu(main4);

    CMenu cs1("Add College ");
    CMenu cs2("Delete College");
    CMenu cs3("View College ");
    CMenu cs4("Back");

```

```
main1.addMenu(cs1);
```

```
main1.addMenu(cs2);
```

```
main1.addMenu(cs3);
```

```
main1.addMenu(cs4);
```

```
CMenu cos1("Add Course ");
```

```
CMenu cos2("Delete Course");
```

```
CMenu cos3("View Course ");
```

```
CMenu cos4("Back");
```

```
main2.addMenu(cos1);
```

```
main2.addMenu(cos2);
```

```
main2.addMenu(cos3);
```

```
main2.addMenu(cos4);
```

```
// CMenu sa1("Read Students");
```

```
CMenu sa2("Allot Seats");
```

```
CMenu sa3("Allotment Details ");
```

```
CMenu sa4("Back");
```

```
//main3.addMenu(sa1);
```

```
main3.addMenu(sa2);
```

```
main3.addMenu(sa3);
```

```
main3.addMenu(sa4);
```

```
CMenu *selmenu= main.showSubMenu(10,10);
```

```
if (selmenu==&cs1)
{
    c1.add_college();
    menu();
}
else if (selmenu==&cs3)
{
    c1.show_college();
    getch();
    menu();
}
else if (selmenu==&cos1)
{
    co1.add_course();
    menu();
}
else if (selmenu==&cos3)
{
    co1.show_course();
    getch();
    menu();
}
else if (selmenu==&cos2)
{
    co1.del_course();
    menu();
}
```

```
else if(selmenu==&cos4)
{
    menu();
}
else if (selmenu==&cs2)
{
    c1.del_college();
    menu();
}
else if (selmenu==&sa2)
{
    a1.allot_seat();
    getch();
    menu();
}
else if (selmenu==&sa3)
{
    a1.display_allotment();
    getch();
    menu();
}
else if(selmenu==&sa4)
{
    menu();
}
if(selmenu==&main4)
    firstmenu();
```

```

    }
}

void menu1()
{
    clrscr();
    closegraph();
    textbackground(WHITE);
    textcolor(BLUE);
    Cwindow w(1,1,79,23);
    gotoxy(3,25);
    printf("ESC -> previous menu");

    gotoxy(45,25);
    printf(" UP / DOWN arrows + ENTER -> select");
    w.showWindow();
    w.setTitle(" ENTRANCE SEAT ALLOTMENT SYSTEM ",BLACK);

    while(1)
    {

        //window to display the menu      x
        Cwindow w1(5,4,71,18);
        w1.setAttributes(DARKGRAY,RED,0,1);
        w1.showWindow();
        w1.setTitle("",BLACK);
        CMenu main;

```

```

CMenu college("College Details");
CMenu course("Course Details");
CMenu read("Input Your Details");
CMenu request("Request For Allotment");
CMenu ext("Exit ");

main.addMenu(college);
main.addMenu(course);
main.addMenu(read);
main.addMenu(request);
main.addMenu(ext);

CMenu *selmenu= main.showSubMenu(10,10);

if(selmenu==&college)
{
    c1.show_college();
    getch();
    menu1();
}else if(selmenu==&course)
{
    co1.show_course();
    getch();
    menu1();
}else if(selmenu==&request)
{
    req.col_request();

```

```

        menu1();
    }else if(selmenu==&read)
    {
        a1.read_details();
        menu1();
    }
    if(selmenu==&ext)
    {
        firstmenu();
    }
}

void graph()
{

    int gd=DETECT,gm=0;
    initgraph(&gd,&gm,"");
}

void firstmenu()
{
    clrscr();
    closegraph();
    textbackground(WHITE);
    textcolor(BLUE);
    Cwindow w(1,1,79,23);

```

```

w.showWindow();

w.setTitle(" ENTRANCE SEAT ALLOTMENT SYSTEM ",BLACK);

while(1)
{

    //window to display the menu
    Cwindow w1(5,4,71,18);
    w1.setAttributes(DARKGRAY,RED,0,1);
    w1.showWindow();
    w1.setTitle("",BLACK);
    CMenu admenu;

    CMenu admin("Adminstrator");
    CMenu user("Candidates");
    CMenu ex("Exit ");

    admenu.addMenu(admin);
    admenu.addMenu(user);
    admenu.addMenu(ex);

    CMenu *selmenu= admenu.showSubMenu(10,10);
    graph();
    if(selmenu==&admin)
    {
        int pwd=get_password();
        if(pwd==1){

```

```

        end();
        closegraph();
        exit(0);
    }
    if(pwd==0){
        menu();
        getch();
    }
}
else if(selmenu==&user)
{
    menu1();
}
else if(selmenu==&ex)
{
    exit(0);
}
}
}

```

PROMENU.cpp

```

#include<iostream.h>
#include<conio.h>
#include<string.h>
#include<graphics.h>

```

```
void readLine(char *str, int size);

// Class containing college Details //

class college
{
    private:
        char cname[25];
        char cplace[25];
    public:
        char ctype;
        int ccode;
        college();
        void add_college();
        void show_college();
        void del_college();
}c1;

class request
{
    public:
        int rkno;
        int col1;
        int col2;
        int col3;
        void col_request();
}
```

```

}req;

// Class containing Reservation Groups //

class reserv
{
    public:
        int mr_seat;
        int sc_seat;
        int obc_seat;
        int ez_seat;
        int mu_seat;
        int nc_seat;
};

// Class containing course Details //

class course:public college,public reserv
{
    public:
        int seatno;
        int cocode;
        char branch[30];
        void add_course();
        void del_course();
        void show_course();
};
}col;

```

```
// Class containing Allotment Details //
```

```
class allotment:public course
```

```
{
```

```
    char br;
```

```
    char st_name[10];
```

```
    int rankno;
```

```
    int res_type;
```

```
    char addr[10];
```

```
    public:
```

```
        void read_details();
```

```
        void allot_seat();
```

```
        void display_allotment();
```

```
};
```

```
// Constructor to initialize data....//
```

```
college::college()
```

```
{
```

```
    ctype=' ';
```

```
    ccode=0;
```

```
    strcpy(cname,"");
```

```
    strcpy(cplace,"");
```

```
}
```

```
// Function to add a new college //
```

```
void college::add_college()
```

```

{
    fstream f;
    int flag=0;
    //f.open("CAS\college.txt",ios::out | ios::app);
    FILE *fp;
    fp=fopen("CAS/college.txt","a");

    Cwindow w5(8,5,65,16);
    w5.setAttributes(LIGHTGRAY,BLACK,7,0);
    w5.showWindow();
    _setcursortype(_NORMALCURSOR);
    textcolor(BLUE);
    if(fp==NULL)
    {
        gotoxy(15,8);
        printf("Canno topen file exiting");
        getch();
        return;
    }
bb:

    gotoxy(15, 8);
    printf("College Type(Eng-e/Med-m) : ");
    gotoxy(45,8);
    cin>>c1.ctype;
    //printf("%c",c1.ctype);

```

```

if(c1.ctype=='m')
    flag=1;
else if(c1.ctype=='e')
    flag=1;
if(flag!=1)
{
    gotoxy(15, 10);
    printf("Enter Type(Eng-e/Med-m), Press any key to continue");
    getch();
    flag=0;
    gotoxy(15, 10);
    printf("                ");
    goto bb;
}

gotoxy(15, 9);
printf("College Code      : ");
gotoxy(40,9);
cin>>c1.ccode;
gotoxy(15, 10);
printf("College Name      : ");
gotoxy(40,10);
cin>>c1.cname;
gotoxy(15,11);
printf("College Place     : ");
gotoxy(40,11);
cin>>c1.cplace;

```

```

        gotoxy(15,11);
        //f.write((char *)&c1,sizeof(c1));
        //f.close();
        fwrite((char *)&c1,sizeof(c1),1,fp);
        fclose(fp);
    }
void college::show_college()
{
    //fstream f;
    int i;
    clrscr();
    //f.open("CAS/college.txt",ios::in);
    Cwindow w5(8,5,65,16);
    w5.setAttributes(LIGHTGRAY,BLACK,7,0);
    w5.showWindow();
    _setcursortype(_NORMALCURSOR);
    textcolor(YELLOW);
    FILE *fp;
    fp=fopen("CAS/college.txt","r");
    if(fp==NULL)
    {
        gotoxy(15,8);
        printf("Cannot open file exiting");
        getch();
        return;
    }
    gotoxy(15,8);

```

```

        printf("  Type      Code      Name      Place");
        textcolor(RED);
        i=9;
        //f.seekg(0,ios::beg);
        //while(f.read((char*)&c1,sizeof(c1)))
        while(fread((char *)&c1,sizeof(c1),1,fp))
        {
            gotoxy(19,i);      printf("%c",c1.ctype);
            gotoxy(34,i);  printf("%d",c1.ccode);
            gotoxy(48,i);  printf("%s",c1.cname);
            gotoxy(66,i);      printf("%s",c1.cplace);
            i++;
        }
        //f.close();
        fclose(fp);
    }

```

// Function to delete a particular college //

```

void college::del_college()
{
    fstream f1,f2,f3,f4;
    int code,ff=0;
    f1.open("CAS/college.txt",ios::in);
    f2.open("CAS/temp1.txt",ios::in | ios::out | ios::app);

```

```

f3.open("CAS/course.txt",ios::in);
f4.open("CAS/temp2.txt",ios::in | ios::out | ios::app);
Cwindow w5(8,5,65,16);
w5.setAttributes(LIGHTGRAY,BLACK,7,0);
w5.showWindow();
_setcursortype(_NORMALCURSOR);
textcolor(BLUE);
gotoxy(15, 8);
printf("Enter College Code  : ");
gotoxy(45,8);
cin>>code;
f1.seekg(0,ios::beg);
while(f1.read((char *)&c1,sizeof(c1)))
{
    if(code==c1.ccode)
    {
        ff=1;
        gotoxy(15, 12);
        printf("Record Deleted !");
        getch();
    }
    else
        f2.write((char *)&c1,sizeof(c1));
}
if(ff==1)
{
    f3.seekg(0,ios::beg);

```

```

        while(f3.read((char *)&co1,sizeof(co1)))
        {
            if(code==co1.ccode);
            else
                f4.write((char *)&co1,sizeof(co1));
        }
        f3.close();
        f4.close();
        remove("CAS/course.txt");
        rename("CAS/temp2.txt","CAS/course.txt");
        f1.close();
        f2.close();
        remove("CAS/college.txt");
        rename("CAS/temp1.txt","CAS/college.txt");
    }
    if(ff==0)
    {
        gotoxy(15, 12);
        printf("College Code does not exist! ");
        getch();
    }
}

// Function to Add a new course //

void course::add_course()

```

```

{
    fstream f1,f2;
    FILE *fp1,*fp2;
    int ff=0;
    int col_code,ts;
    char ty;
    long size;
    int n;
    f1.open("CAS/college.txt",ios::in);
    f2.open("CAS/course.txt",ios::in|ios::out|ios::app);

    Cwindow w5(8,5,65,16);
    w5.setAttributes(LIGHTGRAY,BLACK,7,0);
    w5.showWindow();
    _setcursortype(_NORMALCURSOR);
    textcolor(BLUE);
    gotoxy(15, 8);
    printf("Enter the College Code: ");
    gotoxy(40,8);
    cin>>col_code;
    f1.seekg(0,ios::beg);
    while(f1.read((char *)&c1,sizeof(c1)))
    {
        if(col_code==c1.ccode)
        {
            ff=1;
            ty=c1.ctype;

```

```

                break;
            }
        }
    if(ff==0)
    {
        gotoxy(17, 12);
        printf("College Code Not Exist");
        goto last;
    }
    if(ty=='m')
    {
        gotoxy(18,18);
        printf("MBBS-22,BDS-32,BSc Nursing-42");
    }
    if(ty=='e')
    {
        gotoxy(18,18);
        printf("Mechanical -11,IT-21,Electrical-31");
    }
    col.ccode=col_code;
    gotoxy(15, 9);
    printf("Enter Course Code  : ");
    gotoxy(40,9);
    cin>>col.cocode;
    if(ty=='m')
    {
        if(col.cocode!=22&&col.cocode!=32&&col.cocode!=42)

```

```

        {
            gotoxy(40,9);
            textcolor(RED);
            printf("Invalid course code!!!!");
            getch();
            add_course();
        }
    }
    if(ty=='e')
    {
        if(co1.cocode!=11&&co1.cocode!=21&&co1.cocode!=31)
        {
            gotoxy(40,9);
            textcolor(RED);
            printf("Invalid course code!!!!");
            getch();
            add_course();
        }
    }
    gotoxy(15, 10);
    printf("Enter Course Name  : ");
    gotoxy(40,10);
    cin>>co1.branch;
aa:
    gotoxy(15, 11);
    printf("Total Seat (30 Or 50): ");
    gotoxy(40,11);

```

```
cin>>ts;
if(ts!=30 && ts!=50)
{
    gotoxy(40,11);
    cprintf("enter seat no 30 or 50");
    getch();
    gotoxy(40,11);
    cprintf("          ");
    goto aa;
}
col.ctype=ty;
col.seatno=ts;
if(col.seatno==50)
{
    col.mr_seat=25;
    col.sc_seat=5;
    col.obc_seat=5;
    col.ez_seat=5;
    col.mu_seat=5;
    col.nc_seat=5;
}
if(col.seatno==30)
{
    col.mr_seat=15;
    col.sc_seat=3;
    col.obc_seat=3;
    col.ez_seat=3;
```

```

        col.mu_seat=3;
        col.nc_seat=3;
    }
    f2.write((char *)&col,sizeof(col));
    gotoxy(25,15);
    printf("Course details updated");
    getch();
last:
    f1.close();
    f2.close();
}

// Delete a particular course from a college

void course::del_course()
{
    fstream f1,f2;
    int code,ff=0;
    int c;
    f2.open("CAS/temp1.txt",ios::in | ios::out | ios::app);
    f1.open("CAS/course.txt",ios::in);
    Cwindow w5(8,5,65,16);
    w5.setAttributes(LIGHTGRAY,BLACK,7,0);
    w5.showWindow();
    _setcursortype(_NORMALCURSOR);
    textcolor(BLUE);
    _setcursortype(_NORMALCURSOR);
}

```

```

textcolor(BLUE);
gotoxy(15, 8);
printf("Enter College Code  : ");
gotoxy(45,8);
cin>>code;
gotoxy(15, 9);
printf("Enter Course Code  : ");
gotoxy(45,9);
cin>>c;
f1.seekg(0,ios::beg);
while(f1.read((char *)&co1,sizeof(co1)))
{
    if(code==co1.ccode && c==co1.cocode)
    {
        ff=1;
        gotoxy(15, 12);
        printf("Record Deleted !");
        getch();
    }
    else
        f2.write((char *)&co1,sizeof(co1));
}
if(ff==0)
{
    gotoxy(15, 12);
    printf("No such Entry ! ");
    remove("CAS/temp1.txt");
}

```

```

        getch();
    }
    if(ff==1)
    {
        remove("CAS/course.txt");
        rename("CAS/temp1.txt","CAS/course.txt");
    }
    f1.close();
    f2.close();
}

// Function to show all courses //
void course::show_course()
{
    fstream f;
    int i;
    f.open("CAS/course.txt",ios::in | ios::binary);
    textcolor(RED);
    Cwindow w5(8,5,65,16);
    w5.setAttributes(LIGHTGRAY,BLACK,7,0);
    w5.showWindow();
    _setcursortype(_NORMALCURSOR);
    textcolor(BLACK);
    gotoxy(9,8);
    printf("CollegeCode CourseCode Branch TotalSeat MR SC OBC EZ MU NC");
    textcolor(BLUE);
    i=9;

```

```

f.seekg(0,ios::beg);
while(f.read((char*)&co1,sizeof(co1)))
{
    gotoxy(15,i);  cprintf("%d",co1.ccode);
    gotoxy(26,i);  cprintf("%d",co1.cocode);
    gotoxy(33,i);  cprintf("%s",co1.branch);
    gotoxy(43,i);  cprintf("%d",co1.seatno);
    gotoxy(52,i);  cprintf("%d",co1.mr_seat);
    gotoxy(56,i);  cprintf("%d",co1.sc_seat);
    gotoxy(60,i);  cprintf("%d",co1.obc_seat);
    gotoxy(65,i);  cprintf("%d",co1.ez_seat);
    gotoxy(69,i);  cprintf("%d",co1.mu_seat);
    gotoxy(72,i);  cprintf("%d",co1.nc_seat);
    i++;
}
f.close();
}

```

// Function to read student details //

```

void allotment::read_details()
{
    int ff=0;
    int cocode;
    fstream f,f1;
    f.open("CAS/allot.txt",ios::in | ios::out | ios::app);

```

```

f1.open("CAS/course.txt",ios::in);
Cwindow w5(8,5,65,16);
w5.setAttributes(LIGHTGRAY,BLACK,7,0);
w5.showWindow();
_setcursortype(_NORMALCURSOR);
textcolor(BLUE);
gotoxy(15, 8);
printf("Enter Branch (e/m): ");
gotoxy(40,8);
cin>>a1.ctype;
gotoxy(15, 9);
gotoxy(15, 10);
printf("Course Code      : ");
gotoxy(40,10);
cin>>cocode;
f1.seekg(0,ios::beg);
while(f1.read((char *)&co1,sizeof(co1)))
{
    if(co1.cocode==cocode)
    {
        ff=1;
        break;
    }
}
if(ff==1)
{
    a1.cocode=cocode;
}

```

```

        gotoxy(15, 11);
        printf("Student Name      : ");
        gotoxy(40,11);
        cin>>a1.st_name;
        gotoxy(15, 12);
        printf("Rank No          : ");
        gotoxy(40,12);
        cin>>a1.rankno;
        gotoxy(15, 13);
        printf("Reservation Type : ");
        gotoxy(15,24);
        printf("1 - SC, 2 - OBC, 3 - EZ, 4 - MU, 5 - NC ! ");
        gotoxy(40,13);
        cin>>a1.res_type;
        f.write((char *)&a1,sizeof(a1));
        gotoxy(20,20);
        printf("Request details received");
        getch();
    }
    else if(ff==0)
    {
        gotoxy(30,12);
        printf("No such course on this college");
        getch();
    }
    f.close();
    fl.close();

```

```

}

// Function to allot seats to the students //

void request::col_request()
{
    fstream freq;
    freq.open("CAS/request.txt",ios::in | ios::out | ios::app);
    Cwindow w5(8,5,65,16);
    w5.setAttributes(LIGHTGRAY,BLACK,7,0);
    w5.showWindow();
    _setcursortype(_NORMALCURSOR);
    textcolor(YELLOW);
    _setcursortype(_NORMALCURSOR);
    textcolor(BLUE);
    gotoxy(15, 8);
    printf("Enter Rank No:");
    gotoxy(40,8);
    cin>>req.rkno;
    gotoxy(15, 9);
    printf("Enter 3 Colleges you wish to join:");
    gotoxy(15,10);
    printf("Your First Choice:");
    gotoxy(40, 10);
    cin>>req.col1;
    gotoxy(15,11);
    printf("Your Second Choice:");

```

```

gotoxy(40, 11);
cin>>req.col2;
gotoxy(15,12);
printf("Your Third Choice:");
gotoxy(40,12);
cin>>req.col3;
freq.write((char *)&req,sizeof(req));
freq.close();
}

void allotment::allot_seat()
{
    fstream freq,ft,fcour,fallot,fstud,ftemp;
    freq.open("CAS/request.txt",ios::in);
    fcour.open("CAS/course.txt",ios::in | ios::binary);
    fallot.open("CAS/allot.txt",ios::in);
    ft.open("CAS/modify.txt",ios::app | ios::out);
    ftemp.open("CAS/temp.txt",ios::out);
    int rk1,nd=1,p,md=0;
    int col[3],colg,cour,rtype;
    int coscode,stno,mrst,scst,obc,ez,mu,nc;
    char brh[30],type;
    Cwindow w5(8,5,65,16);
    w5.setAttributes(LIGHTGRAY,BLACK,7,0);
    w5.showWindow();
    _setcursortype(_NORMALCURSOR);
    textcolor(RED);

```

```

gotoxy(15, 8);
cprintf("Enter Rank No:");
gotoxy(40,8);
cin>>rk1;
freq.seekg(0,ios::beg);
while(freq.read((char*)&req,sizeof(req)))
{
    if(rk1==req.rkno)
    {
        col[0]=req.col1;
        col[1]=req.col2;
        col[2]=req.col3;
    }
}
freq.close();
fallot.seekg(0,ios::beg);
while(fallot.read((char*)&a1,sizeof(a1)))
{
    if(rk1==a1.rankno)
    {
        rtype=a1.res_type;
        coscode=a1.cocode;
    }
}
fallot.close();
p=0;

```

cont:

```

fcour.seekg(0,ios::beg);
while(fcour.read((char *)&co1,sizeof(co1)))
{
    if(coscode==co1.cocode&&col[p]==co1.ccode)
    {
        md=1;
        type=co1.ctype;
        colg=co1.ccode;
        cour=co1.cocode;
        strcpy(brh,co1.branch);
        stno=co1.seatno;
        mrst=co1.mr_seat;
        scst=co1.sc_seat;
        obc=co1.obc_seat;
        ez=co1.ez_seat;
        mu=co1.mu_seat;
        nc=co1.nc_seat;
        gotoxy(21,14);    cprintf("merit: %d",mrst);
        gotoxy(21,15);    cprintf("seat : %d",stno);
    }else{
        ft.write((char *)&co1,sizeof(co1));
    }
}
fcour.close();
ft.close();
if(md==1)
{

```

```
gotoxy(21,16);    cprintf("flag: %d",md);
if(mrst>0)
{
    mrst--;
}else
{
    switch(rtype)
    {
        case 1:
            if(scst>0)
            {
                scst--;
            }else
            nd=0;
            break;
        case 2:
            if(obc>0)
            {
                obc--;
            }else
            nd=0;
            break;
        case 3:
            if(ez>0)
            {
                ez--;
            }else
```

```

                nd=0;
                break;
            case 4:
                if(mu>0)
                {
                    mu--;
                }else
                    nd=0;
                break;
            case 5:
                if(nc>0)
                {
                    nc--;
                }else
                    nd=0;
                break;
            }
        }
    ft.open("CAS/modify.txt",ios::app | ios::out);
    col.ctype=type;
    col.ccode=colg;
    col.cocode=cour;
    strcpy(col.branch,brh);
    col.seatno=stno;
    col.mr_seat=mrst;
    col.sc_seat=scst;
    col.obc_seat=obc;

```

```

        col.ez_seat=ez;
        col.mu_seat=mu;
        col.nc_seat=nc;
        gotoxy(21,20);    cprintf("cocode : %d",col.cocode);
        ft.write((char *)&col,sizeof(col));
    }
    ft.close();
    remove("CAS/course.txt");
    rename("CAS/modify.txt","CAS/course.txt");
    if(nd==0)
    {
        p++;
        goto cont;
    }
    if(nd==1)
    {
        fallot.open("CAS/allot.txt",ios::in);
        fallot.seekg(0,ios::beg);
        while(fallot.read((char *)&a1,sizeof(a1)))
        {
            if(rk1==a1.rankno)
            {
                fstud.open("CAS/stud_list.txt",ios::out | ios::app);
                a1.ccode=col[p];
                fstud.write((char *)&a1,sizeof(a1));
                gotoxy(14,17);
                cprintf("Seat Alloted");
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

        }else
        {
            ftemp.write((char *)&a1,sizeof(a1));
        }
    }
    ftemp.close();
}
remove("CAS/allot.txt");
rename("CAS/temp.txt","CAS/allot.txt");
fallot.close();
fstud.close();
}
void allotment::display_allotment()
{
    fstream fstud;
    char br;
    Cwindow w5(8,5,65,16);
    w5.setAttributes(LIGHTGRAY,BLACK,7,0);
    w5.showWindow();
    _setcursortype(_NORMALCURSOR);
    textcolor(YELLOW);
    gotoxy(15, 8);
    int i;
    fstud.open("CAS/stud_list.txt",ios::in);
    textcolor(RED);
    gotoxy(15,8);
    printf("Rank No   Name   Course Code   College Code ");

```

```
textcolor(BLUE);  
i=9;  
fstud.seekg(0,ios::beg);  
while(fstud.read((char*)&a1,sizeof(a1)))  
{  
  
    gotoxy(18,i); cprintf("%d",a1.rankno);  
    gotoxy(24,i); cprintf("%s",a1.st_name);  
    gotoxy(37,i); cprintf("%d",a1.cocode);  
    gotoxy(51,i); cprintf("%d",a1.ccode);  
    i++;  
}  
fstud.close();  
}
```

FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

The proposed system is Common Allotment System. We can enhance this system by including more facilities like increase in the number of options that can be given by a student, the allotment process is fast and user friendly.

Providing such features enable the users to include more comments into the system. The development platform used in this software system uses the powerful features of C++ compiler. This system can be maintained with little efforts and additional functional components can be added in future.

CONCLUSION

The COMMON ALLOTMENT SYSTEM is a great improvement over the manual system which can be affected by transportation problem and regional strikes. The computerization of the system has sped up the process. In the current system, the allotting process is very slow. The common allotment system was thoroughly checked and tested with dummy data and thus is found to be very reliable.

ADVANTAGES

- It is fast, efficient and reliable
- Avoids data redundancy and inconsistency
- Very user-friendly
- Easy accessibility of data
- Number of personnel required is considerably less
- Provides more security and integrity to data

SCREENSHOTS

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. C++ Programming Language (3rd Edition)

Addison Wesley, 1997

2. Let us C++

Yaswant Kanetkar

3. Object Oriented Programming with C++

Balaguruswamy, 2nd Edition

4. Object Oriented Programming in C++,

Robert Lafore

Citations

1. Kamal Acharya. *School management system project report*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.34023165/v1>
2. Kamal Acharya. *A CASE STUDY OF CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.30191075/v1>
3. Kamal Acharya. *A CASE STUDY ON ONLINE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254872.26972790/v1>
4. Kamal Acharya. *Web chatting application project report management system*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.18588592/v1>
5. Kamal Acharya. *RETAIL STORE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.14590154/v1>
6. Kamal Acharya. *SUPERMARKET MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252491.19145062/v1>